

Supplementary Material

Fish lysozyme gene family evolution and divergent function in early development

Lisen Li⁺, João C. R. Cardoso⁺*, Rute C. Félix, Ana Patrícia Mateus, Adelino V. M. Canário and Deborah M. Power*

Comparative Endocrinology and Integrative Biology, Centre of Marine Sciences,
Universidade do Algarve, Campus de Gambelas, 8005-139 Faro, Portugal

Running title: Lysozymes in fish

+ Contributed equally to the study

* Corresponding authors

João C. R. Cardoso: jccardo@ualg.pt

Deborah M. Power: dpower@ualg.pt

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Supplementary Tables:

Supplementary Table 1: Accession numbers of the vertebrate and invertebrate lysozyme C-type and lysozyme G-type sequences used in the analysis. (Please see excel spreadsheet).

Supplementary Table 2: Accession number of the invertebrate lysozyme I-type.

Common name	Species name	accession number
Bivalves		
Asiatic hard clam	<i>Meretrix meretrix</i>	ADL27913.1
Mediterranean mussel	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	OPL33781.1
		AJQ21515.1
		BAF63423.1
		AAN16210.1
Blue mussel	<i>Mytilus edulis</i>	AAN16207.1
Pacific Oyster*	<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	ABB76765.1
		BAF48045.1
		Q6L6Q6.1
		NP_001292276.1
Cockscomb pearl mussel	<i>Cristaria plicata</i>	BAF48044.2
		AFN66526.1
Hydrothermal Vent mussel	<i>Bathymodiolus thermophilus</i>	AFN66527.1
Hydrothermal Vent mussel	<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>	AAN16209.1
Iceland scallop	<i>Chlamys islandica</i>	AAN16208.1
Japanese Scallop	<i>Mizuhopecten yessoensis</i>	CAB63451.1
		XP_021354667.1
Jinjiang oyster	<i>Crassostrea rivularis</i>	XP_021357629.1
Manila clam	<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	ADY38955.1
Venus clam	<i>Cyclina sinensis</i>	ACU83237.1
Eastern Oyster	<i>Crassostrea virginica</i>	AET13645.1
		B3A003.1
		XP_022306813.1
Farrer's Scallop	<i>Azumapecten farreri</i>	XP_022343938.1
	<i>Mizuhopecten yessoensis</i>	ANH58186.1
		XP_021357629.1
Gastropods		
Disk abalone	<i>Haliotis discus discus</i>	AGQ50334.1
		AOX15707.1
Duck clam	<i>Mactra quadrangularis</i>	ADM34988.1
Cephalopods		
California two-spot octopus*	<i>Octopus bimaculoides</i>	XP_014768593.1
Annelida		
echiura	<i>Urechis unicinctus</i>	AWA82039.1
medicinal leech	<i>Hirudo medicinalis</i>	AAA96144.1
	<i>Capitella teleta</i>	R7TR64
		R7TIG0
	<i>Eisenia fetida</i>	AGJ83864.1
	<i>Eisenia andrei</i>	ABC68610.1

Brachiopoda

<i>Adineta vaga</i>	GSADVG00067328001
	GSADVG00026607001
	GSADVG00059746001
	GSADVG00058572001
	GSADVG00066342001

Echinoderm

European starfish	<i>Asterias rubens</i>	AAR29291.1
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Cephalochordate

Amphioxus	<i>Branchiostoma floridae</i>	XP_002602594.1
		XP_002593924.1
		XP_002593923.1

Supplementary Figures:

Supplementary Figure 1: Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree of the fish lysozyme C-type (A) and G-type (B) with the homologues from other chordates and molluscs. To facilitate interpretation of both trees the teleost clusters are annotated. Both lysozyme C-type and G-type trees were rooted using the invertebrate (cephalochordate and mollusc) sequence cluster. To facilitate interpretation the tetrapod (mammalian, bird, reptile and amphibia) branch was collapsed. A) Teleost lysozyme C-type formed three main clusters with the Human LYZ, LYZL1/2 and LALBA. B) Fish Lyg form a single cluster with the tetrapod Lygs. In both trees species that were used for gene environment characterization (Figure 6, 7 and 8) are highlighted in bold. A similar tree was generated using the BI method and is available as Figure 2. A description of the abbreviations used and the accession numbers are available in Supplementary Table 1. * represent transcript sequences.

Supplementary Figure 2: Comparison of the gene organization of the teleost *lyz*, *lyz11/2*, *alba* and *lyg* genes with human. The human, stickleback, zebrafish and sea bass gene structures were compared, and the exon and intron positions annotated based on the predicted gene organization available. Exons are numbered and are represented by boxes and introns are represented by lines.

Human

Stickleback

Sea bass

Zebrafish

Supplementary Figure 3: Comparison of the zebrafish lysozyme C-type A) and G-type B) gene environment with other vertebrates.

The zebrafish lysozyme (*lyz11/2* on chromosome 24 and *lyg1/2/3* on chromosome 14) neighbouring genes were used to search for homologues in other vertebrates (human, chicken, spotted gar and medaka). Lysozyme genes are represented by a solid red arrow. The neighbouring gene families are represented by different coloured blocks. The direction of the arrowheads represents the transcript orientation predicted in the genomes analysed. Genes are mapped based on their actual positions predicted in the genome assemblies. Only genes that are conserved across the different homologous genome regions are represented. Only chromosome region that share at least two genes are represented. A) The human lysozyme C-type members represented are: SPACA5 (A5), SPACA5B (A5B), lysozyme like 1 (L1), Lysozyme-like 2 (L2) and lysozyme -like 4 (L4). The neighbouring genes represented are: polymerase (DNA directed), alpha 1 (*POLAI*), aristaless related homeobox (*ARX*), homogentisate 1,2-dioxygenase (*HGD*), NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit B4 (*NDUFB4*), Pancreatic triacylglycerol lipase precursor (*PNLIP*), Pancreatic lipase-related protein 3 (*PNLIPRP3*), BCLAF1 And THRAP3 Family Member 3 (*BCLAF3*), MAP7 domain containing 2b (*MAP7D2*), eukaryotic translation initiation factor 1A X-linked (*EIF1AX*), Ribosomal Protein S6 Kinase A3 (*RPS6KA3*) and Pyruvate Dehydrogenase E1 Subunit Alpha 1 (*PDHA1*). B) the duplicate human lysozyme G-type genes LYG1 and LYG2 are represented by 1 and 2 in chromosome 9. The neighbouring genes represented are: RAS oncogene family (*RAB33A*), SLIT and NTRK-like family, member 4 (*SLITRK4*), , SLIT and NTRK-like family, member 2 (*SLITRK2*), fragile X mental retardation 1 (*FMRI*), AF4/FMR2 family, member 2 (*AFF2*), iduronate 2-sulfatase (*IDS*), KIAA1210 (*KIAA1210*), E3 ubiquitin protein ligase (*RNF20*), aldolase b, fructose-bisphosphate (*ALDOB*).

A) Lysozyme C-type

B) Lysozyme G-type

Supplementary Figure 4: Relative expression of the gilthead sea bream *lyg1*, *lyg2* and *lalba* during development. Data correspond to the mean \pm SEM of three to six different samples and gene expression levels were normalized using the geometric mean of two reference genes (*18s* and *ef1a*). Two sample group derived from brood stock that showed a divergent growth performance by mid-metamorphosis when are compared. SPSS 25.0 software was used to assess the significance of differences within each experimental group using Two-way ANOVA. Bars with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

lalba

Good growth

lyg1

lyg2

Supplementary Data 1: Multiple sequence alignments of the fish and other metazoan

Lysozyme C- type (A) and Lysozyme G-type (B) that used to build the phylogenetic trees.

A) Lysozyme C-type

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Rty_Lyz1E      MKTLLIISAILTARTKTFERCELARIFKYAGLDGYEGYSLQNWICTAFYESAYNSAALNI
Rty_Lyz1B      MKTFLIISALLTTSPPVYQKCELAQLRRNGLDGYRGSYLANWVCLVQHESNYNTRIVGH
Rty_Lyz1C      MKLILVLSVLLTSSAETLSRCQVVKAIKDSILTKFTHYSVADWVCLAYHESQYNAMEIGH
Rty_Lyz1D      MKLIVLSVLLTSSARVLSRCEFARIKNSILAEPKYSVADWVCMMAHYESQYNTLAKYD
Rty_Lyz1A      MKTLLLSLLLMIDAKVYEKCEFARILKDKGLDGFHRHRLTDWVCMVEIESGYNTALKRH
Cmi_Lyz1C      KTLFVLSLLFLVASAKIYDRCVLARQLKAAGLDGFRGYSLPNWI CMVQHESYNTRATNE
Cmi_Lyz1B      KTLFVLSLLFLVASAKIYDRCVLARQLKAAGLDGFRGYSLPNWI CMVQHESYNTRATNR
Cmi_Lyz1A      KTLFVLSLLFLVASAKIYDRCVLARQLKAAGLDGFRGYSLPNWI CMVQHESYNTRATNR
Mdo_Lyz2      LILLGLVFLPMLAHGKVYERCELARVLKRNGLHGFRSNSVADWVCLAKWESDYNTKATNY
Mdo_Lyz3      LILLGLVFLPMLAHGKVYERCELARVLKQNGMDGFGGNSLADWVCLAKWESDYNTKATNY
Mdo_Lyz1      LILLGLVFLPMLAHGKVYERCELARILKQNGMDGYRGISLANWVCLAKWESNYNTRVYNY
Mmu_Lyz2      LLTLGLLLSVTAQAKVYNERCELARILKRNMGMDGYRGVKLDADWVCLAQHESYNTRATNY
Mmu_Lyz3      LLTLGLLLSVTAQAKVYERCEFARTLKRNGMAGYGVSLADWVCLAQHESYNTRATNY
Hsa_LYZ       LIVLGLVLLSVTVQGVFERCELARTLKRNGMDGYRGISLANWVCLAKWESYNTRATNY
Mmu_Lyz1      LLTLGLLLSITIQGVYDRCSLARTLQSLGLAGFQGITLANWVCLAKWESNFNTNTTRF
Apl_Lyz1      -----HISARRGDGVCMTSWSFNTQATNR
Apl_Lyz2      -----HISARRGDGVCMTSRSGFNTQATNR
Gga_Lyz       LLILVLCFLPLAALGKVFGRCELAAMKRHGLDNYRGSYSLGNWVCAAKFESNFNTQATNR
Psi_Lyz1      LLILGLVLLPLAAPGKIYEQCELAREFKRHGMDGYHGYSLGDWVCTAKHESNFNTAATNY
Psi_Lyz2      LLILGLFLLPLAAHGKIYERCELARAMKRLGLDGYWGYSLGNWVCTARFESQFNSTATNY
Xtr_Lyz       VLFWGGIFIFTVTDGKVFERCELAGIMKKMGLDGYRGSYSLPNWVCTAFFESSFYTDRTNF
Oni_Lyz2      MRSLLVLLFLAVANAKIFERCEWARTLKANGMDGYGYSLADWVCLTRWESNYNTMAKNT
Oni_Lyz3      IKSLLFLLLVAVANAKRFQRCCEWAHKLKDSGMDGYRNI SLADWVCLTKWESGYDTMKTHH
Oni_Lyz1      RSVFVFLLLITVASAKVFERCDWARKLKANGMDGYRGSYSLANWVCLTKHESNYNTKATNR
Pfo_Lyz2      TKTLVLLLVAVANAKVFERCAWARTLKASGMDGYRGISLADWVCLTQHESHFNTRATNR
Pfo_Lyz3      MKTLLVLLLVAVANAKVFERCAWARTLKASGMDGYRGISLADWVCLTQHESHFNTRATNR
Pfo_Lyz4      MKTLVLLLVAVANAKRFQRCCEWARTLKASGMDGYRGISLADWVCLTQHESGYDTMKTHH
Xma_Lyz2      TKTLVLLLVAAAANAKVFERCAWARTLKANGMDGYHGISLADWVCLTQHESNFNTNVKYR
Pfo_Lyz1      LVVPAVLLLAAVVDGRVFERCQWARTMKSNGMDGYRDISLANWVCLTYWESGYNTLAVNH
Xma_Lyz1      LVVLAVLLLAAVVDGRVFERCQWARTMKNYGMMDGYWGISLANWVCLTYSESSYNTTAVNH
Cse_Lyz       IKGVVLLLVALLSVAVVYERCTWAKLLKSQGMDFHGISLPNWWVCLTNWESHFNAINH
Ola_Lyz       MKSLVFLLLVAGASAKVFERCQWARLLKAQGMMDGYRGSYSLANWVCLTQHESRFNAINH
Nro_Lyz       MRSLVFLLLVALLASAKVYERCEWARVLKAHGMMDGYGNSLADWVCLSKWESSWTTSTNH
Gac_Lyz       MRVVVFLLLVAAAGAKVYERCEWARVLKANGMDGYGGYGLADWVCLSYSESGYSTTATNF
Aja_Lyz       MRALVFLLLVAVASAKVFERCELARTLKAAGMDGYRGSVLDWVCLARWESSYNTAATNR
Srh_Lyz       MRCLLFLLLVAVAGAKVFERCELARLLKSYGMNRYRGISLADWVCLSQWESSYNTRATNR
Tru_Lyz       YSLFLLVLLVAVANAKVFERCEWARVLKARGMDGYRGISLADWVCLSKWESQYNTNAINH
Tni_Lyz       MRTLVFLLLVAVASAKVYQRCCELARVLKSQGMMDGYRGISLANWVCLSKWESSYNTNAINH
Dla_Lyz       MRSLVFLVLANARTYQRCCEWARVLKNNGMMDGYHGYSLANWVCLTQHESNYNTGAINH
Pol_Lyz       MRTLVVLLLVAVANARVYERCEWARLLRNQGMMDGYRGISLANWVCLTEWESHYNTRATNH
Omy_Lyz       MRVVVLLLVAVASAKVYDRCELARALKASGMDGYAGNSLPNWWVCLSKWESSYNTQATNR
Ssa_Lyz       MRVVVLLLVAVASAKVYDRCELARALKAYGMDGYAGNSLPNWWVCLSKWESSYNTQATNR
Loc_Lyz       MKFVVFLCLFALANCKVYDRCELARKLKASGLDGYRGSYSLPNVCLSKWESTYNTTAINH
Aca_Lyz1A     -WSLVLLACLVLGQGEYLSRCEVAQQLQQLGMDGYAGYSLANWVCTAFHESFNTQAMHY
Lch_Lyz1C     --LLIPLLLLVASGMVYSRCELARVLQAGMNGYWGYSLGNWLCMSYYESGYNTQAIDH
Cca_Lyz11_2_2 VTIAVLCLMWLCCESRRLKRCDDVVRIFKQEGLDGFEFSGVGNVCTAYWESRPFKTHRVR-
Cca_Lyz11_2_3 VTIAVLCLMWLCCESRRLKRCDDVVRIFKQEGLDGFEFSGVGNVCTAYWESRPFKTHRVR-
Cca_Lyz1_2_1  VAIAVLCLMWLCCESRRLGRCDVARIFKQEGLDGFEFSGVGNVCTAYWESRPFKTHKVR-
Dre_Lyz11_2_1 LAVVFLCLAWMSCESKTLGRCDVYKIFKNEGLDGFEGFSGVGNVCTAYWESRPFKTHRVR-
Dre_Lyz11_2_2 LAVVFLCLAWMSCESKTLGRCDVYKIFKNEGLDGFEGFSGVGNVCTAYWESRPFKTHRVR-
Cid_Lyz11_2  VAIAVLCLMWMSCESRTMGRCEVVKIFRAEGLDGFEGFSLGNVCTAYWESRPFKQVR-
Ame_Lyz11_2  KLVI VLCVMFLACESRTMSRCEVARAFKAQGLDGFEGFALGNVYVCMFWSKWKTHKVR-
Hsa_LYZL2     MKAAGILCLVTGAESKIYTRCKLAKIFSRAGLDNYWGFSLGNWICMAYYESGYNTTAQTV
Hsa_LYZL1     KSVGVFALIIISVAESKIYTRCKLAKIFAKAGLDNYGGFALGNWLCMAYYESHYNTTAEV
Mmu_Lyz11_2  LVLLLSYLLTPIGASILGRCTVAKMLYDGLNYFEGYSLENWVCLAYFESKFNPSAVYE
Mmu_Lyz14     MKASVVLYLVVPSGAYILGRCTVAKKLHDDGLDYFEGYSLENWVCLAYFESKFNPMAYE
Hsa_LYZL4     LKALFICVASCVNDGNIHRCSLAKILYEEDLDGFEGYSLPDWLCLAFVSNFNISKVNE
Mmu_Lyz16     LLIYLVSSFLALNQASLISRCDLAQLQLEDLDGFEGYSLSDWLCLAFVSNFNISKVNE
Hsa_LYZL6     LLLQFLLCFASRTGAKVFERCELAKMLKNYGLDGYRGSYLANWVCMMAFYESGFDTKMVRP
Aca_Spaca3    VSLVLLATLASGNMGKIFQRCCELAQVLHAGMDGFRGYSLADWVCLAFHESRFDTGTVDH
Psi_Spaca3    ALAYLLSCLLASSKAKVFSRCELAKEMHDFGLDGYRGNLADWVCLAYYTSGFNTNAVDH
Mmu_Spac3     AGIMLLACLPSSEAKLYGRCELARVLHDFGLDGYRGSYSLADWVCLAYFTSGFNAAALDY
Hsa_SPACA3    QTLVLLACFVEATQAKIFDRCLAHVLDKNGLDAFEGISLADWICMAFFESGFDTEAIDW
Aca_Lyz1D     ALLFLVSLIMANEAKIFSRCELAVILHEEGLDGYEGYSLANWICMAFFESGFDTEAIDW
Psi_LyzL4_6   LAFVLLCLFIAVSEAKVYEKCELAKILKISKMDVSSGYSLDNWVCLAYHESRFDKAVGP
Aca_Lyz1B     LAFTFLCFLFIAVNEAKVYERCELARLKNRSLDVSSGYSIADWVCLAYYESRFSRAVGP
Aca_Lyz1C     MKAWGTVLMVVTVDAKIYERCELAARLERAGLNGYKGYGVGDWLCMAHYESGFDTAFVDH
Hsa_SPACA5    MKAWGTVLMVVTVDAKIYERCELAARLERAGLNGYKGYGVGDWLCMAHYESGFDTAFVDH
Hsa_SPACA5B   MKAWGTVLMVVTVDAKIYERCELAARLERAGLNGYKGYGVGDWLCMAHYESGFDTAFVDH
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Dre_Lyz11_2_2 -SDTGKDYGIFQINSFKWCDDGTP-GKNLCKVACSDLLNDDLKASVECAKLI VKMDGLKS
 Cid_Lyz11_2 -TDVGKDYGIFQINSFKWCDDGTP-GKNLCLNLPDSDLLKDDLKPSVECAKLI VKTGGGLKS
 Ame_Lyz11_2 SDDSGKDYGIFQINSFKWCDDGTANGQNLRCRVPCGDLLNNDLQASVECAKLI VKREGGLKA
 Hsa_LYZL2 LDDGSDYDYGIFQINSFAWCRRGKLENNHCHVACSALVTDDLTDAL ICAKKIVETQGMNY
 Hsa_LYZL1 LDDGSDYDYGIFQINSFAWCRRGKLENNHCHVACSALITDDLTDAL ICAKKIVETQGMNY
 Mmu_Lyz11_2 LEDGSTDYGIFQINSFTWCRNARKKHQKNHCHVACSALITDDLTDAL ICAKKIVKET-----
 Mmu_Lyz14 DDPDGTGFGLFQIRDNNEWCGHGK----NLCSVSTALLNPNLKDTIQCAKKIVKGGHMGMA
 Hsa_LYZL4 NREGYTGFGFLQMRGSDWCGDGR----NRCHMCSALLNPNLEKTIKCAKTI VVKEGGMGA
 Mmu_Lyz16 NVDGSDYDYGIFQINSRYWCNDYQSHSENFCHVDCQELLSPLNLI STIHC AKKIVVSG-----
 Hsa_LYZL6 NADGSDYDYGIFQINSRYWCNDYKSYSENLCVHVCQDILLNPNLAGIHC AKKIVGARGMNN
 Aca_Spaca3 QDNGSTSNIGIFQINSYLWCEDYKHYTPNICQMHCSDLLTSYIRDDVACAMRIVQGGKGLGA
 Psi_Spaca3 EADGSTDNGIFQINSRLWCEDYKSSARNLCHMHCSDLLTSNINDDIVCAMQIVQQRGLGA
 Mmu_Spac3 EADGSTNNGIFQISSRRWCRTLASNGPNLCRIYCTDLLNNDLKD SIVCAMKIVQELGLGY
 Hsa_SPACA3 EADGSTNNGIFQINSRRWCSNLTTP-VPNVCRMYCSDLLNPNLKDTVI CAMKI TEPQGLGY
 Aca_Lyz1D HNDGTDYDYGIFHINSRWCKDLDSSENLCMNCCKLSDDDI TDDINCAKRI VQDQSMGA
 Psi_Lyz14_6 NADGSTDYGMFQINSRVWCNNYRSPTEENLCHIPCTDILLNNDI ADDIACA KRI VQDQMDA
 Aca_Lyz1B PNDGSRDYGIFQINSRWCSNGEGTTANGCKTSCSAFTTDDI TDDITCAKRI VQDNGIRA
 Aca_Lyz1C PNDGSRDYGIFQINSRWCSNGEGTTANGCRSSCSAFTD DDI TNDIACA KRI VQDNGIRA
 Hsa_SPACA5 NPDGSEYDYGIFQINSAWWCNDGITPTKNLCHMDCHDLLNRHILDDI R ICAKQIVSQNGLSA
 Hsa_SPACA5B NPDGSEYDYGIFQINSAWWCNDGITPTKNLCHMDCHDLLNRHILDDI R ICAKQIVSQNGLSA
 Mmu_Spaca5 NPDGSEYDYGIFQINSAWWCNDGITPTQNL CNIDCNLLNRHILDDI ICAKRVASSKSKMKA
 Lch_Lyz1A NHDSSDYGILQINSYWCEDG-TPSRNICGIDCNLSDNDI SDDIACA KRI VQDQMDA
 Lch_Lyz1B NHDSSDYGILQINSRWCEDEG-TPSKNLCRIDCNKFTDEDI TDDLQCA KRI VQDQMDA
 Mmu_Lalba -DNGSTEYGLFQISDRFWCKSSEFPSENICGISC DKLLDDELDDDI ACA KRI I LAIKGIDY
 Hsa_LALBA -NNESTEYGLFQISNKLWCKSSQVPSRNICDI SCDKFLDDDI TDDIMCA KRI I DIKGLDY
 Mdo_Lalba -NNGNTEYGLFQISNNGWCAEKQEDAKSTCGILCSKLLDDDI INDDIACA KRI I EQKGLDY
 Aca_Lyz1F -PTRRKAYGLFRINNSDWCSGVDGQPSKNL CNISCSKLIDDDI KDDILCA KRI I KQGHLLKA
 Ano_Lyz1E -GPRATNHGIFLLSSRWWCND SKTPPRNYCNISCEALQDSDI ADDITCAK KRI VVQKGFKA
 Hdi_Lyz1A NSGGSSDYGIFQINSYWCNDGGRKT-KNGCGHPCSDYLNSNIGDDVTCVKQLLREGGWGF
 Hdi_Lyz1B NSGGSSDYGIFQINSYWCNDGGRPT-YNGCGHPCSDYLNTYLGDDI QCI RQLLREGGWGF
 Lgi_Lyz1 NRDGSADHGIFQINDYWCNDGGRKT-KNGCKHPCTDFENSSLD D D VRCMKTLLG---WQH
 Bfl_Lyz1C PNDGSDYDYGIFQINDHYWCNDGPP--HNDCGVSCSNLRDNNI ADDVRC AKLI YQRHG FSA
 Bfl_Lyz1D PNDGSDYDYGIFQINDHYWCNDGPP--HNDCGVSCSNLRDNNI ADDVRC AKLI YQRHG FSA
 Bfl_Lyz1B PNDGSDYDYGIFQINDHYWCNDGPP--HNDCGVSCSNLRDNNI ADDVRC AKLI YQRHG FSA
 Bbe_Lyz1 PNDGSDYDYGIFQINDYWCNDGPP--HNDCGVSCSNLRDNNI ADDVRC AKLI YQRHG FSA
 Bfl_Lyz1A PNDGSDYDYGIFQINGYWCNNRKNPN--HNDCGVSCYDLD DDI ADNVKCVKLI YKRHG FFA
 Mga_Lyz1B NSG-SKDYGIFQINSKFNCGSSTIRNTYGCADSCSTLNSDI SNDAYCAVRI KCKGGFSK
 Mga_Lyz1C NSG-SKDYGIFQINSKFNCGSSTIRNTYGCADSCASLTNSDI SNDAYCAVRI KCKGGFSK
 Mco_Lyz1 NSG-SKDYGIFQINSYKNGSSSTRNTYGCADSCSSFTSDSI SNDANCAVVRKNCAGFGR
 Mga_Lyz1A NSDKSIDYDYGIFQLNK YWCDDT SKKNTCGCTDTCTSLIDSDI SNDACAVQVKNCDFDE
 Csi_Lyz1 NSNGSKDYGIFQINDGFWCGSGTIRRTNGCQDSCSSFLNSDI SNDANCAVRIKNCDFGFSR
 Sau_Lalba DPSNHVDYGLFQLSNHLVCSGDESPPH-LSG-----
 Dla_Lalba SSDGCTLYGLFQLSSHLVCSGDSPPN-ICGMDCSELTD DNI QDDI SCV LKIFTDNGFGA
 Oni_Lalba GLDDDTLYGIFQLWDQLVCGNGTNPPI-I-----
 Nco_Lalba RRRGSVDYGLFQLSDHLICSDGATPPDRICNVTC SALVDDDI EDDIGCVLNI ISNGGFAM
 Pol_Lalba KKENS I WY G I F Q L S D H L I C S D G Q T P S L N K C G K N C T D L L D S D I S D D I D C L L E T L N K L G F T A

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Rty_Lyz1E WYKVPFFVFL-----
 Rty_Lyz1B WYSWKKKCQSRNLGDFLDDCKI
 Rty_Lyz1C -----
 Rty_Lyz1D WQGWAANCKGKWI DY YTF FCFW
 Rty_Lyz1A WPGWEEVHGERPQSIG----
 Cmi_Lyz1C WYGWRDHCRGRNLQRYVQGCNV
 Cmi_Lyz1B WYGWRDHCRGRNLQRYVQGCNV
 Cmi_Lyz1A WYGWRDHCRGRNLQRYVQGCNV
 Mdo_Lyz2 WVAWRNHCEGRDVSSYIRGC SL
 Mdo_Lyz3 WVAWRNHCEGRDVSSYIRGCGL
 Mdo_Lyz1 WVAWRNRCQGKNLSSYIQGCRL
 Mmu_Lyz2 WVAWRNRCQNRDLSQYIRNCGV
 Mmu_Lyz3 WVAWRNRCQNRDLSQYIRNCGV
 Hsa_LYZ WVAWRNRCQNRDVRQYVQGCNV
 Mmu_Lyz1 WAGWIKHKCNKLNKEYIRGC HL
 Apl_Lyz1 -VAWRNRCRGTDVSKWIRGCRL
 Apl_Lyz2 -VAWRNRCRGTDVSKWIRGCRL
 Gga_Lyz WVAWRNRCRGTDVQAWIRGCRL
 Psi_Lyz1 WVAWTKYCKGKDV SQWIKGCCL
 Psi_Lyz2 WVAWTRNCKGRDVSQWIRGCGL
 Xtr_Lyz WVGWRNHCKGRDLSQWIKDCCL
 Oni_Lyz2 WYGWRSNCDGRDLSYVSGCGV
 Oni_Lyz3 WYGWRSHCQGRDLAPYLDGCGL
 Oni_Lyz1 WSRLGSHCRGSYLT SF LRGCA-
 Pfo_Lyz2 WVAWTTHCQNRDLSYLSGCRL
 Pfo_Lyz3 WVAWRKYCQNRDLSYLRGCRL
 Pfo_Lyz4 WVAWRNRCQNRDLSYLRGCRL
 Xma_Lyz2 WVAWRRHCCQNRDLSYLRGCRL
 Pfo_Lyz1 WVGWRMHCKNQDVSQYVQGCGL

Xma_Lyz1	WVGWRTHCKNQDVSKYLDGCGL
Cse_Lyz	WVAWRVHCQGRDLSEYIRGCVL
Ola_Lyz	WVAWRDHCRGRDVSSYIQGCGF
Nro_Lyz	FTSEPVDCVTLRKPQSSAASCRP
Gac_Lyz	WVGWRNHCEHRDVSSYLAGCRL
Aja_Lyz	WVAWRAHCEGQDVSSQYIAGCGV
Srh_Lyz	WVAWKSHCEGRDLSPYLAGCGV
Tru_Lyz	WVAWNRHCQNRDLSAYIAGCGL
Tni_Lyz	WVAWNRNCQGRDLSGYVAGCGL
Dla_Lyz	WVAWRRYCQNRDLSSYVAGCGL
Pol_Lyz	WVAWRQHCQGDLSYLAGCGL
Omy_Lyz	WVAWRLHCQNDLRSYVAGCGV
Ssa_Lyz	WVAWRLHCQNDLRPYVDGCGV
Loc_Lyz	-VAWNRNCQGRDLSQYTAGCGV
Aca_Lyz1A	WVAWRLHCQGDLSYVEGCVL
Lch_Lyz1C	WLSYNNRQRNGGLSNYIVGCEA
Cca_Lyz11_2_2	WDTWGSYCKGRKMSRWVKGCEE
Cca_Lyz11_2_3	WDTWENYCKGRKMSRWVKGCEE
Cca_Lyz1_2_1	WDTWDSYCKGRKMSRWVKGCEE
Dre_Lyz11_2_1	WETWDSYCNCRKMSRWVKGCEQ
Dre_Lyz11_2_2	WETWDSYCNCRKMSRWVKGCEQ
Cid_Lyz11_2	WETWDSYCNCRKMKRWTKGCEC
Ame_Lyz11_2	WDTWDKYCNCRKLSRWVKSCDV
Hsa_LYZL2	WQGWKKHCEGRDLSWKKDCVF
Hsa_LYZL1	WQGWKKHCEGRDLSWKKGCEV
Mmu_Lyz11_2	-----
Mmu_Lyz14	WPIWSKNCQLSDVLRWLDGCCL
Hsa_LYZL4	WPTWSRYCQYSDLARWLDGCCL
Mmu_Lyz16	-----
Hsa_LYZL6	WVEWRLHCSGRPLFYWLTGCRL
Aca_Spaca3	WKMWKKNCEGEDVDIWLKGCCL
Psi_Spaca3	WLAWRKHCEGRDLSQWVEGCNV
Mmu_Spac3	WEAWRHHCQGRDLSWVDGCGF
Hsa_SPACA3	WEAWRHHCQGDLTEWVDGCGF
Aca_Lyz1D	WNQWKMHCQDQDLFRWVKGCCL
Psi_LyzL4_6	WEDWTMHCKGRDLSWVDGCDL
Aca_Lyz1B	WVAWVNHCCEGRDLSWTKDCSL
Aca_Lyz1C	WVAWVKYCQGNLTRWTQGCRL
Hsa_SPACA5	WTSWRLHCSGHDLSEWLKGCCL
Hsa_SPACA5B	WTSWRLHCSGHDLSEWLKGCCL
Mmu_Spaca5	WDSWTQHCAHDLSEWLKGCCL
Lch_Lyz1A	WLVYGTIKKHHLQERLDGSG-
Lch_Lyz1B	WNGWKNCKGKDVSEFVEGCGV
Mmu_Lalba	WKAYKPMCSEKLEQWRCEK---
Hsa_LALBA	WLAHKALCTEKLEQWLCEK---
Mdo_Lalba	WKAHKTFCLENLDQWRCLN---
Aca_Lyz1F	WPRWAKRCRGKDLVSVKSCNF
Ano_Lyz1E	WRRAWERNCKGQDLTQYIAGCEF
Hdi_Lyz1A	SYGHGAQCSS-VTSSYLSGCTY
Hdi_Lyz1B	SYGYADKAS-VTSSYLSECSL
Lgi_Lyz1	SYGYAARCKG-VTASYLSGCSY
Bfl_Lyz1C	WYGWQNNCQG-STSSYVSGCF-
Bfl_Lyz1D	WYGWQNNCQG-STSSYVSGCW-
Bfl_Lyz1B	-----
Bbe_Lyz1	WYGWINHCQG-HNNANLVTSCW
Bfl_Lyz1A	WYGWVNKCGG-DTTSYVKDCW-
Mga_Lyz1B	WNGWKDYCSNVQGSEYYSTC--
Mga_Lyz1C	WNGWKDYCSNVQGSEYYSTC--
Mco_Lyz1	WYGWKDHCNVDQSEYYSSTC--
Mga_Lyz1A	WYGWRDHCANVQSSEYFSDC--
Csi_Lyz1	WEGWKNCKGKLNKPPSGC--
Sau_Lalba	-----
Dla_Lalba	FKAYQEECRDVKASDYFTDCTL
Oni_Lalba	-----
Nco_Lalba	KPKFQPECDNETAVHYFAECKD
Pol_Lalba	WEEFLPECIEKKPSEYFSDCR-

B) Lysozyme G-type

Apl_Lyg1 CYGDINALQAPTISCAGIAAVRRRTADADI IRLRKYEIPIKRVARNLCLDPALIAAIIISQE
Gga_Lyg3 CWPTEERRCASSGLSAGLALRRRTVEADVIRLRRYEVPIKRVARRLCLDPALIAAIIISQE
Mdo_Lyg1 CYGNIRNIDTPGASCCGVRASERLAEMDLPYVQRYQPTLRLVGRKYCLDPAVIAGILSRE
Mmu_Lyg1 TYGNIRTLDTPGASCCGVRASERLAEDRYPYLLRHQPTMRLVGGQKYMCDPAVIAGVLSRE
Hsa_LYG1 CYGNIQSLDTPGASCCGVRASERLAEDMPYLLKYQPMQITIGQKYCMDPAVIAGVLSRK
Hsa_LYG2 CYGDIIMTKTSGATCCGIRGSEMFAEMDLRAIKPYQTLIKEVQQRHCVDPAVIAAIIISRE
Mmu_Lyg2 CYGDIIMTMEFTGAPCCGIHSGSEMFAEMDLKAIKPYRILIKEVQQRHCIDPALIAAIIISRE
Mdo_Lyg2 CYGDVMRMDTPGASCCGIRGSELFAEMDLALMMKYQTMIKTVGQKQCVDPALIAAIIISRE
Ola_Lygb EYRNLEEMRTTGVSALGVEGSEILAKKDLKPMKSKYRNQIMNVGRKRLRHPALIAAMISKQ
Pfo_Lygb EYRNLSQMTTGTGASKTGVVSKMLAQDLELMSKYKDKIKSVGKALRRLHPALIAAIIISKQ
Tni_Lygb EYGHHTTCLETSERGTEASNIIAAKDLKMMKFKDDITSVGQRLGVPEPALIAAIIISRQ
Sau_Lyg3 TYGDIIMRVETSGASLSGVRASNAERDLNEINKYKSTINNVAEKRVHPALIAALISRS
Sau_Lyg4 TYGDIIMRVETSGASLSGVRASNAERDLNEINKYKSTINNVAEKRVHPALIAALISRS
Dla_Lyg1 SYGNIMKVETTGASESGVRASSAMAETDLEKMKDYKSI IKNVARQKIDPALIAAIIISRS
Ssa_Lyg3 RYGNIMDVETSGADLEGPASHRMAEHDLAAMNKYKGLIMKVAERNAVDPAVICGIIISRE
Ssa_Lyg5 TYGDIIMKVETTGASKSGVSASERMAEDDEDDVKYIDI I KEVKGKENEIAPALICGIIISRE
Gmo_Lyg3 TFGDILKVETTGASEKGVTAASEIMAKEDLDSMKKYKTI IKNVAERRHVNPALIAAGIIISRE
Tru_Lyg3 SYGNIMSIETSGASAPGIQGSREMARIDLERMKYKSI I RQAGQKQCVDPALIAAGIIISRE
Tru_Lyg2 SYGNIMSIETSGASAP---GHEMARIDLERMKYKSI I RQAGRECDVDPALIAAGIIISRE
Tru_Lyg1 SYGKIEDIKETSGASDGGWKSHRMAEIDSNRMENYRTI I NEAGKQCVDPALIAAGIIISRE
Tni_Lyga AYGNIMKISTTGASAVGVAASEKMAQIDVERMRYTGI I SRAAQKQCVDPALIAAGIIISRE
Pfo_Lyg1 SYGDIITRVSASGASESGVEASEKMAQMDSGRMNKYKSKINSVGSQCGIDPALIAAIIISRE
Pfo_Lyg2 SYGDIITRVSASGASESGVEASEKMAQTDGSRMKNYKSKINSVGSQCGIDPALIAAIIISRE
Xma_Lyg SYGDIINRVEASGASEFGVRASETMAQTDGSRMKNYKSKITRVSQSGIDPALIAAIIISRE
Pol_Lyg SYGQIRLVETSGASGSGVKASHKMAEIDSGRMSKYKSKINKVGGQSYGIEPALIAAIIISRE
Sma_Lyg GYANIKDVQTTGASWSGVEASHTMAETDGRMSRYKSKIFNVGQKCGIDPALIAAIIISRE
Nro_Lyg2 GYASVMRVETSGASWSGVAASHTMAQTDGSRMANYRSKINSVGGQSGIEPALIAAIIISRE
Nco_Lyg4 GYASVMRVETSGASWSGVAASHTMAQTDGSRMANYRSKINSVGGQSGIEPALIAAIIISRE
Nro_Lyg1 -----GGRSVSRDMAQTDADRMMKYRSKINKVAKQHNIDPALIAAIIISRE
Gac_Lyg RYGDIMKVPTTGASLAGEKASHTLAQTDKNRMEKYRSKINTVGAQYIDPALIAAIIISRE
Dla_Lyg2 AYGNIMRVETTGASWSGKASHTMAQTDAGRMEKYRSKINKVGGSCGIDPALIAAIIISRE
Dla_Lyg3 DFGDIMKVETTGASQSGVKASHTMAQTDADRMEKYRSKINKVGGSCGIDPALIAAIIISRE
Sau_Lyg2 GYGNIMRVETTGASESGVKASHRMAEIDADRMEKYRSNINRVGGYIDPAIAAIIISRE
Lcr_Lyg GYGNIMRVQTTGASESGVKASQAMAELDAGRMEKYRSKINSVGRYDIDPALIAAIIISRE
Ola_Lyga VFDIRNVSTTGASASGVSASHAMAQTDAGRMMRYKDKITAVGHRLGVDPALIAAIIISRE
Sau_Lyg1 SYGNIMDVETTGASATGVKASHKMAETDADRMEKYKSKINSVGVKYGIDPAIAAIIISRE
Nco_Lyg2 NNGDIMRVETDGASRGGRSVSRDMAQTDADRMMKYRSKINRVAKHNIDPALIAAIIISRE
Cse_Lyga SFGNINRIPTSGASWKGAKASQTLAETDSRMMKYRDKI I RVANETGIQPCPLIAAIIISRE
Xtr_Lyg1 QYGDINKVPTSGASCCGVQASERMAQTDLTRMNRYSI IESVSRKMGMDAALIAAGIIISRE
Cse_Lygb GYGSVLDVETSGASAAGVEASHTMAKTDLQRMERYKAI I KEVGRKYGVEPALIAAIIISRE
Gmo_Lyg6 GYGDIMRVETSGASNGGVQASEKMANHDLACMRTYKTI IGVKASKRDVDPALIAAIIISRE
Gmo_Lyg1 GYGDIMRVETSGASNGGVQASREMANHDLACMRTYKTI IGNVARRRNVDPALIAAIIISRA
Gmo_Lyg5 EYGNIMNVETSGASSGGVQASEKMASDDLDRMESYKTI IGNVARKHDVDPALIAAVASRE
Gmo_Lyg4 GYGDIMTVITEGASDAGVPASQKMAKDDLGNMETYKTI IENVAKRHDVDPALIAAGIIISRE
Gmo_Lyg2 GYGDITQVETSGASSDGVRASTMAQTDAGRMEKYKSFINNVAKHVVDPAVIAAIIISRE
Gmo_Lyg7 GYGDIMQVEMSGASSDGVRASTMAQTDARRMEKYKSFINNVAEKHDVDPAVIAAIIISRA
Ssa_Lyg2 RYGDIMGVDTTGASWSGVSASHEMAKDRPYVDKYKGRITSAGQKYGVDPAVLGGIIISRE
Aja_Lyg4 IYGDVNRIDTTGASQQGVSASHELARTDLSRVNQYKDAIQRAAQDQHDPAVVAIIISRE
Psi_Lyg1 CYGDINKVDTTGASCCGINASAKMAEKDLPTMNNYKAI IKNASRAICMDPAVITGIIISRE
Psi_Lyg2 CYGDIITKVDTTGASCCGVQASEKIAEKDLNMMNKYKAI I KGTGLKTCVDPALIAAGIIISRE
Psi_Lyg4 -----MTFPLTTGVRASAEIARKDLSRMNRKYKTI I IKSAAKCYVDPVSVVAGIIISRE
Psi_Lyg3 CNGNINDVDTTGASSSGVRASAEIARKDLDRMKYKPMI I SAARKHNMDPAVIAGIIISRE
Gga_Lyg1 CYGSVSRIDTTGASCCGVRASRTI AERDLGSMNKYKVLIKRVGEALCIEPAVIAGIIISRE
Apl_Lyg2 CYGSVNRIDTTGASCCGVPASKIAERDLKAMDYKTLIKKVGKLCIEPAVIAGIIISRE
Gga_Lyg2 FYGNIANVETTGASQAGVAASEKIAERDLKNMDKYKETITKVANSKICPPSLVAAVIISRE
Bfl_Lyg1 SYGNIMAVDTTGASAGGVSASNQMASTDLHRLNLYKSKIYDAANAKSMDPAVIAAIIISRE
Bfl_Lyg2 NYGNIMAVDTTGASAGGTSASQQMARTDLNRLNLYKSKIYNAASAKNMDPAVIAAIIISRE
Bfl_Lyg3 -YGNILVVDTTGASATGVAASHQMASTDLRSLNLYKSKIYLAASAKNMDPAVIAAIIISRE
Lch_Lyg1 IYGNVNMIDTTGASQTPVASHKMAENDSGRMCKYKTRILEVGRKQMDPAVIAAIIISRE
Lch_Lyg2 NYGNVNMIDTTGASKGGKLASRMAETDSARMEKYKDI I VVKVGAKNIDPAVIAAIIISRE
Pma_Lyg CYGDLMNIDTTGASIRGVAASKLVNADLMLKKNYKTI I VATANAKCNDPAVIAAIIISRE
Rty_Lyg VYGDITKVDTTGASERGVAAASHKMMSTDLERVNKYKTLIEKAACANQIDLAI I SAI ICRE
Ssa_Lyg1 CFGDITKVDTSGASEQGVDAESHKLAEHDLVRMKNYKELITRVGQKHGLDPAIIAGIIISRE
Omo_Lyg LFGDIMKVETSGASEKGVASHKMAEHDMKRMQYKSMVQTVGHSKGLDPAIIAGIMSRE
Ame_Lyg1 TYGDIITKVPTTGASEKGVASHKMAEHDLKRMQYKSI I ITRVGAQKQMDPEVIAAIIISRE
Ame_Lyg2 IFGDVMMKIDTTGASEKGVASHKMAEHDLKRMQYKSI I ITRVGAQKQMDPEVIAAIIISRE
Tfu_Lyg IYGDVMMKIDTTGASDQGVASHKMAEHDLKRMQYKSI I ITRVGAQKQMDPEVIAAIIISRE
Aja_Lyg2 IYGDVMMKIDTTGASEQGVAAASHKLAEHDFSRMKTYYRDI I I KVGRQQMDPAVISGIIISRE
Aja_Lyg3 IYGDITKVPTTGASQGVASHKLAESDLTRMKNYKDVITKVAKAHKIEPAVIAGIIISRE
Cid_Lyg IYGDVMMKIDTTGASDQGVASHKLAEHDLARMEKYKSI I I KVGRKQMDPAVIAAIIISRE
Dre_Lyg2 IYGDIMKIDTTGASEKGVASHKLAEHDLARMEKYKSKILKVARAKQMDPAVIAAIIISRE

Dre_Lyg1 IYGDIMKVGTGASKTGEVASKKLAEHDLARMEKYKTKIINVGRAKQMDPAVIAAIIISRE
Cca_Lyg SGIDIMKIDTTGASEKGEVAPKLAEHDLARGEKYKNMITKVGAKKMDPAVIAAMISRE
Dre_Lyg3 SGIDIMKIDTTGASEKGEVASKKLAADDFVRMEKYKCKIFKVAKEKDVPALIAAIIISRE
Bgl_Lyg2 CYGDINNLSPTGRKVGVPKSNSEVQTDLTYLNRYSYQTAADKLCIQASVIAAVASRE
Pac_Lyg CHGDIDQLHPTGKHTGGVAGSNAEVQHDLPALNNHRSCYQASADTNCIQASVIAALASRE
Aca_Lyg1 CHGNVMDLSPTGQKSGGVSASNSDAQADITYLNKYKTCFQKVAVSQCIQASLIAALASRE
Myc_Lyg3 CHGDVRRLLHPTGEHNGGVAASNDVDYDLHDLNKKSCYASGAHAIQPSVIAALASRE
Myc_Lyg1 CHGDVRRLLHPTGEHNGGVAASNDVDYDLHDLNKKSCYASGAHAIQPSVIAALASRE
Afa_Lyg CHGDVRRLLHPTGEHNGGVAASNDVDYDLHDLNKKSCYASGAHAIQPSVIAALASRE
Myc_Lyg2 CHGDVRRLLHPTGEHNGGVAASNDVDYDLHDLNKKSCYASGAHAIQPSVIAALASRE
Air_Lyg CHGDVRRLLHPTGEHNGGVAASNDVDYDLHDLNKKSCYASGAHAIQPSVIAALASRE
Mga_Lyg2 CHGNVTVLHPRGMAPGGMAASHLAIDQDITTEIDKRKSCYLKAAANNCIHPAVIAGIASRE
Mco_Lyg CHGNVTVLHPRGMAPGGMAASHLAIDQDITTEIDKRKSCYLKAAANNCIHPAVIAGIASRE
Mga_Lyg1 CHGDVTVLHPTGMG--GMAGSHQADIDQDIAEINKRSCYVQAGAANCIPAVIAGIASRE
Hdi_Lyg1 CYGDVMMKLRPTGASSSGVQASNHMVDQDYAELNKRKSCYVRAGANNCIHPAVVAGVASRE
Hdi_Lyg2 CYGDVMMKLRPTGASSSGVQASNHMVDQDYAELNKRKSCYVRAGANNCIHPAVVAGVASRE
Lgi_Lyg1 CHGDVMMKLRPTGASSSGVQASNHMVDQDYAELNKRKSCYVRAGANNCIHPAVVAGVASRE
Aca_Lyg CHGNVTVLHPTGMG--GMAGSHQADIDQDIAEINKRSCYVQAGAANCIPAVIAGIASRE
Lgi_Lyg2 CYGDVMMKLRPTGASSSGVQASNHMVDQDYAELNKRKSCYVRAGANNCIHPAVVAGVASRE
Lgi_Lyg3 CHGDVMMKLRPTGASSSGVQASNHMVDQDYAELNKRKSCYVRAGANNCIHPAVVAGVASRE
Cbe_Lyg CHGNVTVLHPTGMG--GMAGSHQADIDQDIAEINKRSCYVQAGAANCIPAVIAGIASRE
Cgi_Lyg CFGDVTVLHPTGKSNNGVQSSQLDVSKTYNLAHSYKACFEQIGFTFCIHPAVIAGIASRE
Hdid_Lyg LYGDITKISPKGASASGVAASQALVDADIAELDKLDIFVRVGESLNIHPALIGAIASRE

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Apl_Lyg1 SRAGLLDNGWDQGRQRFLMQIDRRQPYGTWDSSEHINQCSTMLVLGINEMRVRHPTWTW
Gga_Lyg3 SRAGLLDNGWDQGRQRFLMQIDRRQPYGTWDSSEHINQCSTMLVLGINEMRVRHPTWTW
Mdo_Lyg1 SQGGNLSV--GGNVASGIGLVQPGGIQOPTYWTSETRASQVSENLMRIKEIRRYPTISA
Mmu_Lyg1 SPGNNVVD--LGNIGSGLGMVKETKFYPPTAWKSETWVSQKTQTLTSSIKEIKTRFPWTWA
Hsa_Lyg1 SPGDKLVN--MGDRS---MVQDPSQATSWISESQVSQTEVLTTRIKEIQRRFPWTWP
Hsa_Lyg2 SHGSLQDQGDWHRGLKFGMLQDLKQHPVGAWDSKEHLSQATGILTERIKAIQKFPWTSV
Mmu_Lyg2 SHGALQNGWDHKGQRFLMQDLKHPVGAWDSKEHLSQATGILTERIKAMKRPWTWNT
Mdo_Lyg2 THAGSLQDQGDWHRGLKFGMLQDLKHPVGAWDSKEHLSQATGILTERIKAIQKFPWTSV
Ola_Lygb SNAGQLKDGGMHNSYGLMQINRKFVAVGEPFSEHDHIDEGSTYLIHLIKTVNWRPDWSR
Pfo_Lygb SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Tni_Lygb SQAGTSSGYSVNDNCFGLMQINKHYAVGNAYSSEHIDQGVTFILQIKTRRRTRPDWSK
Sau_Lyg3 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Dla_Lyg1 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Ssa_Lyg3 CRAGLKRGR--YDNSYGLMQINGDTTKVPFDFSEHLLLEGTNILYFIRIKNAFPDWSK
Ssa_Lyg5 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Gmo_Lyg3 TEAGFINKGWGDKGNFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Tru_Lyg3 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Tru_Lyg2 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Tru_Lyg1 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Tni_Lyga SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Pfo_Lyg1 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Pfo_Lyg2 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Xma_Lyg SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Pol_Lyg SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Sma_Lyg SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Nro_Lyg2 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Nco_Lyg4 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Nro_Lyg1 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Gac_Lyg TRAGNLQGGWGDGNAWGLMQVNGGTTARGSWDSVEHLSQATGILVNFIDRISKKFPWSW
Dla_Lyg2 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Dla_Lyg3 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Sau_Lyg2 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Lcr_Lyg SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Ola_Lyga SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Sau_Lyg1 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Nco_Lyg2 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Cse_Lyga SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Xtr_Lyg1 SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Cse_Lygb SRAGLNDKGYGKLDVCFGLMQIDKRIKDYELGTAFSREHIDQGSTCLHLIKDMKIQKPDWSE
Gmo_Lyg6 SRGGAISGGWCPRRIGFGLMQVDKDTPIGAWNSVEHVDQATGILVDIIKEVQRDFPDWSR
Gmo_Lyg1 TRGGAISGGWGDGNAWGLMQVNGGTTARGSWDSVEHLSQATGILVNFIDRISKKFPWSW
Gmo_Lyg5 SRGGAISGGWGDGNAWGLMQVNGGTTARGSWDSVEHLSQATGILVNFIDRISKKFPWSW
Gmo_Lyg4 SEAGHINKGWGDNNAWGLMQVNDKRRPRGAWDSEHLDQGTGILVDFIKHVKQKERNWST
Gmo_Lyg2 SRAGNIFNGWGDNYNGFGLMQVDKREPRGAWNSEEHDQATGILVNFIDRISKKFPWSW
Gmo_Lyg7 SRAGNIFNGWGDNYNGFGLMQVDKREPRGAWNSEEHDQATGILVNFIDRISKKFPWSW
Ssa_Lyg2 SRGGTFLVNGSGDNGNAWGLMQVNDKRRSPKGAWDSQEHIDQGAQILAGSYSDVERKHPWP
Aja_Lyg4 TRGGMSDQGDHGYAFGLMQVDKRRPEGEWNSQQHINQGTKILASFINQMKAKFPWSK
Psi_Lyg1 SNAGTLKDGWDELGNKFGMLQIDKHQLFGPWNSKVHLIQGTGILADNLIKIQKFPWTK
Psi_Lyg2 SHAGALKNGWGDGNAWGLMQVDKRNKIVGRWNDEHLLDATRIFIGMINGIKAKFPKWTI
Psi_Lyg4 SHAGALKNGWGDGNAWGLMQVDKRRPVGKWNQSEHLDQGTGILVSMINGIKRKPWTK
Psi_Lyg3 SHAGLENGWGDHGNFGLMQVDKRRPVGKWNQSEHLDQGTGILADNINTIEDKFPWTK

Gga_Lyg1 SHAGKLNKNGWDRNGFGLMQVDRKRKIEGTWNGEAHIRQGTTRILIDMVKKIQKFPWRTR
Apl_Lyg2 SHAGTLKGGWGDNGNGFGLMQVDRKRKLGQGTWNGEAHITQGTILINFIKRIQKFPNWTK
Gga_Lyg2 SHAGTLKGGWGDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRKPHGAWDSEEHIKQGTIDILCQSITDIQKFPWTSK
Bfl_Lyg1 SRAGALADGTGDHNGYGLMQVDIRTPGGPYSTAHMRQGTQILIDTINCVRKNHPGWTO
Bfl_Lyg2 SRAGALADGTGDNGNGYGLMQVDIRTPGGPYSTTHIKQGTQILIDTINCVRKNHPGWST
Bfl_Lyg3 TRAGALADGTGDNGNGFGLMQVDYRTPGGPYSTEHEMMQGTQILIDTINCVRKHPGWTA
Lch_Lyg1 SRAGALHDGWDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRTPVGAWDSEEHISQGTQILIDMITSIQKFPGWTL
Lch_Lyg2 TRAGGLTKGWDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRTPVGAWDSEEHISQGTQILIDMITSIRKNFPWRTL
Pma_Lyg SRAGALVKGFGDNGNGFGLMQVDRKRIVGTWDSHDLKQGTGILIDMISAIKPKFPNWTQ
Rty_Lyg SRGGNLKNGWGDHGNAGFGLMQVGSKTKIGTWTSEHLQGTQILIDMITSIQKFPGWTL
Ssa_Lyg1 SRAGSLDHGWDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRIVGAWDSEKHISQGTQILIDMITSIRRIQAKFPAPWK
Omo_Lyg SRAGALVNGWGDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRKLVGEWDSKEHVNQATGILVDFINTIQKFPKPKPK
Ame_Lyg1 SRAGALVNLGDKNGNGFGLMQVDRKRTPRGAWNSEEHIVQGTGILIKAITDIQKFPSPWK
Ame_Lyg2 SRAGALVDGWDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRTPKGAWNSEEHVQGTQILIDLIQIKQKFPSPWL
Tfu_Lyg SRAGALVNGWGDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRPRGTWDSSEHIRQGTQILIDMITSIQKFPKPKPK
Aja_Lyg2 SRAGALKDGDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRTPRGAWNSEEHVQGTQILIDFIKIKQSKFPDWPK
Aja_Lyg3 SRAGALVNGWGDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRSPKGEWNSEHQVTQGTQILIDMITSIQKFPSPWK
Cid_Lyg SRAGALIDGWDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRTPKGAWNSEEHVQGTQILIDFIKIKAKFPQWTO
Dre_Lyg2 SRAGALKDGDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRKLVGAWDSEEHVQGTQILIDMITSIQKFPPTWTK
Dre_Lyg1 SRAGALKDGDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRTPVGAWDSEHQVLTQATEILIDFIKIKAKFPKWSQ
Cca_Lyg SRAGALKNGWEPAGNGFGLMQVDRKRTPVGAWDSEHQVLTQATEILIDFIKIKVNFPKWTO
Dre_Lyg3 SRAGHLKNGWGDHGNAGFGLMQVDRKRTPVGAWDSEHQVLTQATEILIDFIKIKAKFPKWSL
Bgl_Lyg2 SRGGSLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIKNPCVSWNSCAHIEMMTGALIAKINEVKKKFPNWP
Pac_Lyg SRGGSLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIKNCCGWDSCHVEMMVRILVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Aca_Lyg1 SRGGSLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWDSEEHVQVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Mye_Lyg3 SRGGRLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWDSEEHVQVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Mye_Lyg1 SRGGRLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWDSEEHVQVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Afa_Lyg SRGGRLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Mye_Lyg2 SRGGRLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Air_Lyg SRGGRLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Mga_Lyg2 SRAGKMLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Mco_Lyg SRAGKMLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Mga_Lyg1 SRAGKMLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Hdi_Lyg1 TRGGKLLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Hdi_Lyg2 TRGGKLLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Lgi_Lyg1 TRGGKLLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Lgi_Lyg2 TRGGKLLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Lgi_Lyg3 TRGGKLLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Cbe_Lyg SRGGALNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWTD
Cgi_Lyg TNVGAVSRGWNAGHFYEGMLPCDTRSTCYPWNTCDHALMMAQVLLPFVKSITQKFPSPWLS
Hdid_Lyg SRAGTLNLYGDDGKAYGIMQCDIRYSCYAWNSCEHIEQMVSVLVPIVNSVVRKFPSPWLS

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Apl_Lyg1 DQQLRGGICAYRARIGNI-QVYDEDPGCRDNSYVNSVIGRAQYFKRHGF
Gga_Lyg3 DQQLRGG-ICTYHARAGNL-QIYDEDPGCRDNNYVNSVIRRAQYFKRHGF
Mdo_Lyg1 DQYLRRGGLCAYSEGPG-----YVRSNQDFSCDFCNDVRLARARYKGGHGF
Mmu_Lyg1 DQHLRRGGLCAYSKGPN-----FVRSNQDLNCFDNDVRLARAKYFKDHGF
Hsa_Lyg1 DQYLRRGGLCAYSGGAG-----YVRSNQDLNCFDNDVRLARAKYFKRHGF
Hsa_Lyg2 AQHLKGGLSAFKSGIE-----AIATPSDIDNDFVNDIARAKFYKRQSF
Mmu_Lyg2 AQQLKGGLTAFKSGME-----TIVTPADIDGDLVDDVRLARAKFYKRHGF
Mdo_Lyg2 SQHLKGGLYAYRSGID-----ALVTPDVENYDNTDILARCKFYRRHGF
Ola_Lygb EQHLKGGALVCMVGLLEKEKLYDELQDPTPRDFANDVIARAQFYAENGF
Pfo_Lygb EMQLKGGALVAYMTGLDRVLDPDHLDSETRTKDFSNDIARAQFFEQKGY
Tni_Lygb EQQLKGGALACYVAGEERVALYEDLDSVTPSKDFSSDVVARAHWFAQNGF
Sau_Lyg3 EQQLKGGIAAYHAGPLAIHSYEEVDAKTYGGDYSDVVARAQWYKSEGF
Sau_Lyg4 EQQLKGVFYLTNCLHTVLCVTHLYLSFQE-----
Dla_Lyg1 EQQLKGGIAAYNAGDGNHHSYEEVDAKTTGCDYSNDVIARAQWYKRNNGF
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Ssa_Lyg5 EQQLKGGIAAYNQDGAIDSCEEVDENTTGKDYSDVVARAQWYHTNLV
Gmo_Lyg3 EEQLKGGALAAYNKGDGVVHSYKNDVENTTGKDYSDVVARAQWYWDNLV
Tru_Lyg3 NQHLKGGIAAYNMGDQNVRSYETVDAATTRDYSNDVVARAQWYKRY--
Tru_Lyg2 NQHLKGGIAAYNMGDQNVRSYETVDAATTRDYSNDVVARAQWYKRY--
Tru_Lyg1 DQHLKGGALAAYNKGEKNVESYASVDAKTTGKDYSDVVSRAQWYKSNGF
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Xma_Lyg EQQLKGGIAAYNTGDGKVHSYENVDEKTTGKDYSDVVARAKWYKRNNGF
Pol_Lyg EKQLKGGIAAYNMGDKNVHSYEGVDENTTGKDYSDVVTARAQWYRDNGY
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Sau_Lyg2 EQQLKGGIAAYNMGDGNVHSYENVDGSTTGKDYSDVVARAQWYKRNNGF

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 Nco_Lyg2 EQQLKGGIVAYNVGDGKVKNYKAVDYTTTHGDYSDVVARAKHWYKEKDY
 Cse_Lyga EHQLKGAIAAYNQDGDGKVSFENVDETTGKDYSDVVISRALWYQRNGY
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 Cse_Lygb EQQLKGGIAAYNAGDQRVSTN-VDEYTTGGDYSDVVARAQWYKNGY
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